

Harmonizing Pain: Ayurvedic Insights and Management Strategies

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Abstract: Pain, an essential warning system of the body, serves as a protective mechanism signaling harm or distress. In Ayurveda, pain, known as Shoola, originates primarily from Vata Dosha, as stated by Acharya Sushruta. Ayurvedic understanding of pain is deeply rooted in Tridoshas, Triguna, Srotas, and Ojas, with connections to past life Karma, as described by Maharishi Charaka.

Ayurvedic texts classify pain into various forms such as Shoola (piercing), Dank (bursting), Vedana (unbearable sensation), Dagdha (burning), Chosa (sucking), Nirmathan (churning), Shastravidh (cutting), and Spandana (vibration), each influenced by associated Doshas altering their nature and intensity.

In modern medicine, pain often signifies inflammatory processes, and the conventional use of NSAIDs carries significant risks, including gastrointestinal bleeding, increased stomach acid, damage to the protective mucus layer, and renal complications, particularly in high-risk individuals.

Ayurvedic treatments focus on bio-purification of body channels, immune stabilization, and psyche management, aiming to strengthen the body's inherent healing mechanisms without adverse effects when administered according to Ayurvedic principles.

To summarize, Ayurveda's approach to pain management emphasizes holistic healing, channel purification, and immune enhancement, providing a safer alternative to conventional treatments while addressing the root cause of pain.

Keywords: pain, ayurveda, management, panchakarma

Introduction

Pain is a symptom of mental and physical hurt or disease. The International Association for the Study of Pain defines pain as- 'An Unpleasant sensory and emotional experience arising from actual or potential tissue damage. In Ayurvedic classical text Sushrut Samhita we found terms such as Shool, Ruj, Vedana and Rukrevealing condition of Pain. Similarly, in Charak Samhita Angmardprashaman (10 drugs used in treatment of Body ache), Shoolprashaman & Vednasthapak Mahakashaya is mentioned. This article elaborates various treatment modalities mentioned in Ayurveda in context to pain management such as Snehan (Oleation), Swedan (Fomentation), Agnikarma (Heat burn Therapy), Jalaukaavcharan (Leech therapy), Vedhankarma (needle puncturing), Lepa (medicated paste), Bastikarma (enema) is discussed. This article will be useful for the research scholars who are exploring the role of Ayurveda in the pain management.

Concept of pain in ayurveda

In Ayurveda, pain is understood as a complex phenomenon arising from imbalances within the body's vital energies, known as doshas. Among the three doshas - Vata, Pitta, and Kapha - Vata is considered the primary culprit behind most types of pain. According to Ayurvedic principles, when Vata becomes imbalanced or aggravated, it can disrupt the natural flow of energy and circulation within the body, leading to various forms of discomfort and pain. The concept of pain in Ayurveda extends beyond the physical sensation to encompass the emotional and psychological aspects as well. It is believed that pain arises not only from physical causes but also from disturbances in the mind and emotions, as well as from external factors such as diet, lifestyle, and environmental influences. Ayurvedic texts classify pain into different categories based on its characteristics and underlying causes. These may include piercing pain (Shoola),

burning pain (Dagdha), throbbing pain (Vedana), and others. The specific qualities and location of the pain help Ayurvedic practitioners identify the doshic imbalances and formulate appropriate treatment strategies.

Ayurvedic treatment approaches for pain management focus on restoring balance to the doshas through various therapies, including herbal remedies, dietary modifications, lifestyle changes, and specialized treatments such as Panchakarma (detoxification therapies). These interventions aim to address the root cause of pain while promoting overall health and well-being. In addition to physical interventions, Ayurveda also emphasizes the importance of addressing the mind-body connection in pain management. Practices such as yoga, meditation, and mindfulness are often recommended to help individuals cope with pain, reduce stress, and promote relaxation.

Overall, the concept of pain in Ayurveda is multifaceted, acknowledging the interconnectedness of the body, mind, and spirit in health and disease. By addressing the underlying imbalances and promoting holistic well-being, Ayurveda offers a comprehensive approach to pain management that goes beyond symptom relief to support long-term health and vitality.

Snehan Karma:

Snehan (oleation) is mentioned as Purvakarma and practiced before all Panchkarma procedures. Due to Sneh(oleation) VataDosh gets pacified. Bahya Snehan or Abhyangais application of oil on the skin which is again divided into Sarvanga Snehan(whole body massage) or SthanikSnehan (application of oil locally to the affected part like Janubasti, Katibastior Manyabasti etc As per the modern perspective, the Neuro-hormonal effects of BahyaSnehan has been established, stating that massage increases levels of Dopamine, increases availability of serotonin, may elevate epinephrine (adrenaline) and release of endorphins. (Research conducted at TOUCH Research Institute at the University of Miami). All these neuro-hormones alter brain chemistry which in turn reduces response to pain sensation.

Swedan Karma:

Swedana, a traditional Ayurvedic therapy, serves as a valuable tool in pain management by harnessing the therapeutic benefits of sweating to alleviate discomfort, promote relaxation, and enhance overall well-being; this technique involves the application of heat through various methods such as steam, hot packs, or herbal poultices to induce sweating, dilate blood vessels, improve circulation, and facilitate the release of toxins and metabolic waste products from the body, thereby reducing inflammation, relieving muscle tension, and promoting healing; Swedana therapy encompasses different modalities including Nadi Swedana (steam therapy), Bashpa Swedana (sitting in a steam chamber), and Pinda Swedana (herbal poultice therapy), each tailored to individual needs and conditions; by increasing blood flow to affected areas, Swedana enhances the delivery of nutrients and oxygen to tissues, accelerates the removal of pain-inducing substances, and stimulates the body's natural healing mechanisms, making it effective for a wide range of painful conditions including arthritis, muscle strains, and sciatica; the deeply relaxing nature of Swedana also helps alleviate stress, anxiety, and tension, promoting a sense of calmness and well-being; when incorporated into a comprehensive treatment plan, Swedana therapy offers a natural, non-invasive approach to pain management that addresses both the physical and emotional aspects of discomfort, empowering individuals to experience relief, restore balance, and optimize their health and vitality.

Agnikarma Therapy:

Agnikarma (Heat burn Therapy) is one of the para surgical procedure described for the pain management. Agnikarma helps in relieving pain in painful conditions specially Musculoskeletal pain such as heel pain, Osteoarthritis, Frozen shoulder etc. Agnikarma, leads to pacification of Vata & Kapha Dosha, thereby reducing pain. Similarly, Agnikarma pacifies Manda Dhatvagni and facilitates Amapachanand increases the Dhatvagni, thereby, metabolite toxins are removed. Thus, pain caused by the accumulation of metabolic waste products in the tissues is immediately relieved after Agnikarma Therapy.

Raktamokshan by Jalauka:

Jalaukaavcharan (Leech therapy) involves application of Jalauka (Leeches) for removal of vitiated blood at the site of pain. It is proved by various researches that the sensory stimulus caused by the pain and burning sensation of the leech bite can alleviate the symptoms of the patient through the “gate theory”. The main components of Medicinal Leech saliva is Hirudin which inhibits blood coagulation by binding to thrombin, Bdelins acts as anti-inflammatory and inhibits trypsin, Eglins acts as anti-inflammatory and inhibit activity of cathepsin G, Carboxy-peptidase A inhibitors increases the inflow of blood at the bite site, Histamine like substance, acetylcholine acts as vasodilator and Anesthetic substance which causes anesthesia at the bite site.

Raktamokshana, a therapeutic procedure rooted in Ayurveda, entails the application of medicinal leeches known as Jalauka to specific points on the body, serving as a centuries-old remedy for pain relief, inflammation reduction, and enhanced blood circulation; the therapeutic efficacy of Jalauka lies in its saliva, which contains a diverse array of enzymes and bioactive substances that collectively exert analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, and vasodilatory effects, providing a comprehensive approach to pain management and healing; by attaching themselves to the skin and releasing their saliva, leeches facilitate the inhibition of pain signals, the reduction of inflammatory mediators, and the dilation of blood vessels, thus improving the flow of blood and lymphatic fluid while relieving pain and discomfort; the analgesic properties of leech saliva, attributed to enzymes such as hirudin and destabilase, play a pivotal role in dampening pain perception and alleviating symptoms associated with various conditions, including arthritis, joint pain, back pain, and migraines; in addition to its analgesic effects, leech therapy exerts potent anti-inflammatory actions by modulating the release of inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukins and tumor necrosis factor-alpha, thereby mitigating tissue inflammation and swelling; the localized nature of leech therapy allows for targeted treatment of pain and inflammation, minimizing systemic side effects and promoting efficient healing of affected tissues; enhanced blood circulation induced by Jalauka therapy facilitates the removal of metabolic waste products and toxins from the body, promoting tissue regeneration and reducing the risk of complications associated with stagnant blood flow; while Jalauka therapy is primarily indicated for pain management, it also finds utility in the treatment of conditions characterized by blood stasis, such as varicose veins and thrombosis, owing to its ability to promote blood flow and prevent clot formation; when administered by trained practitioners using sterile techniques, leech therapy is generally safe and well-tolerated, with minimal risk of adverse reactions or complications; however, it is essential to exercise caution and adhere to strict hygiene protocols to prevent infections and ensure the optimal therapeutic outcome of Raktamokshana by Jalauka; in conclusion, Raktamokshana by Jalauka represents a valuable therapeutic modality in Ayurveda, offering a natural and holistic approach to pain management and healing, underpinned by centuries of traditional wisdom and empirical evidence.

Viddhan karma:

Vedhan karma is one of the eight Shastrakarma (surgical measures) mentioned in Sushrut Samhita. In Viddha karmathe points are pierced with special hollow needles which leads to painful mechanical stimulus which causes release of endorphins thereby, causing immediate pain relief. Few Ayurveda experts are practicing a modified Agnikarmaprocedure named-Viddhagni, by clubbing Agnikarma& Vedhan karmatogether. However, there is no validated document available to prove its supremacy over the conventional Agnikarma therapy. Lepam chikitsa: This is application of medicated paste over the painful body parts. Sushruta has described Lapanin Twakgatvata, MansagataVata and in management of pain due to Vranshophya. The mechanism of action of lepan can be explained with the Mechanism of transduction of cold thermoreceptors as for example Menthol sensation is perceived via TRPM8 channel; whereas role of Pradehacan be explained with TRPV1 channels and furthermore certain Warm receptors also being sensitive to painful stimuli function as non receptors.

Basti chikitsa:

In Bastikarma, the medicinal dravyasare administered into the rectum of the patient. Since, every Pain is attributed to vitiated Vata Doshaand in order to correct this imbalance Bastiis the main (prim) treatment modality amongst the Panchkarmatherapies. It is hypothesized that Bastikarma has a feature to regulate sympathetic activity, thereby, balancing the autonomic nervous system.

Hypothalamus-Pituitary-Adrenal axis (HPA) gets activated with the visceral afferent stimulation, involving the release of neurotransmitters from adrenal gland called cortisol, a neuroendocrine hormone, acts as a potent anti-inflammatory systemically. Basti Chikitsa, a pivotal component of Ayurvedic therapy, plays a crucial role in pain management by administering medicated enemas to rectify imbalances and alleviate discomfort through direct absorption of therapeutic compounds into the bloodstream, addressing the root cause of pain while enhancing overall health and well-being; categorized into Niruha Basti and Anuvasana Basti, this therapy utilizes herbal decoctions and oils to mitigate inflammation, relax muscles, regulate Vata dosha, and nourish tissues, making it effective for diverse painful conditions such as arthritis, sciatica, and gynecological disorders, while its personalized approach tailors treatments to individual needs, optimizing outcomes and ensuring a holistic, sustainable solution for pain relief and improved quality of life.

Palliative treatment(ShamanChikitsa)in the management of pain :

The main objective of palliative treatment is to correct the vitiated Vata Dosha. Further, to resolve this Vata imbalance and pain Madhur, Amla & Lavan Rasa (taste) herbs are prescribed. This concept can be better understood through the knowledge of receptors on cells that mediate Taste & Pain both. G-Protein Coupled Receptors are dynamic machines for signaling Pain. These same group of receptors (T1R2 & T1R3 receptors) are responsible for perception of Sweet taste (MadhurRasa) thereby, making us understand the role of Madhur Rasa in resolution of pain. As regards, Lavan(Salty taste -ENaC Receptors)& Amla(Sour taste -Two TRP channels –PKD2L1, which are also present in pain fibres responding to chemical stimuli like Capsaicin & menthol) use ion channels-proteins that form a channel through which specific inorganic ions can diffuse. Changes in cellular ion concentrations could then be detected and transmitted to the nervous system. However, Dr. Charles Zuker, meanwhile, states that current ion channel theory is not correct and GPCRs could also be involved in these perception modalities. In a nutshell, the role of GPCR in mediation of pain and mediation of taste thereby, explaining the role of Madhur, Amla and Lavan Rasa in the Pain management.

Conclusion

This article aims to investigate the traditional Ayurvedic understanding of pain, juxtaposed with modern scientific insights. It seeks to reassess Ayurvedic pain management strategies, validating their efficacy in current contexts Agnikarma, Jalaukaavcharan, Vedhankarma, Lepankarma, Bastikarma are discussed followed by brief narration of Shaman chikitsa in Pain followed by Satvavjay chikitsa with Dietary & Lifestyle modification inculcating Yog & Meditation Practices in life helps one to understand the modulation of pain in light of modern concepts. Many other facets of vitiation Vata Dosha & Pain as for example treatment of Vatavyadhi (disorders due to vitiated Vata Dosha) chiefly are out of purview of this article. The management of Pain itself is still under research persistently as it is a subjective parameter with different threshold for different individuals. Current article is an attempt to cover the maximum aspects of Pain treatment & throw an emphasis on probable mode of action of the chief therapeutic procedures utilized in pain treatment in Ayurveda but as the symptom being subjective; it depends on the patient, site, extent and stage of the disease and hence doesn't offer the most appropriate modality for pain relief. To conclude, it is a Herculean task to cover entire concept of Pain management in Ayurveda. There are few distinct formulations and therapies mentioned in classical text (Sushrut Samhita) for pain management such as Shatphal Ghritam and Hingvadi Gutika in Udarshool (Abdominal colic), Siravedh chikitsa (Bloodletting through venipuncture) in Gridhrasi (Sciatica), Vardhman pippali in Vatarakta (Gouty arthritis) which needs therapeutic validation leaving a scope for future research in pain management through Ayurveda.

REFERENCES

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Association_for_the_Study_of_Pain [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
2. Caraka, Shadvirechanshatahritiya adhyay. In :Vaidyamanorama Hindi Commentary, AcharyaVidyadhar Shukla, Prof.Ravi Dutt Tripathi, CarakaSamhita Purvarardha Sutrasthana, 2nd ed. Varanasi :Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan; 2007. p. 77,4:44,45,47.
3. <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/anaesthesia/StudentsandTrainees/PainPathwaysIntroduction>
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pain> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
5. <http://www.blackwellpublishing.com/patestas/chapters/10.pdf> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
6. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/neuroscience/spinothalamic-tract> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
7. <http://nba.uth.tmc.edu/neuroscience/s2/chapter08.html> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
8. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4695672/#B51> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
9. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4695672/> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
10. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/G_protein%E2%80%93coupled_receptor [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
11. <http://www.health24.com/Medical/PainManagement/About-pain/Physiology-ofpain20120721> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
12. <http://www.caringinfo.org/i4a/pages/index.cfm?pageid=3513> [Last accessed on 19/01/2018]
13. Susruta, Gulmapratishedh. In: Prof. K.R.SrikanthaMurthy, Susruta Samhita uttarardha, 2nd ed. Varanasi :Chaukhamba Orientalia ; 2005.p.271,42:81
14. Sushruta, Aampakwaishaniya adhyay. In : Prof.K.R.Srikantha Murthy, Susruta Samhita Sutrasthanam, 2nd ed. Varanasi: ChaukhambaOrientalia; 2005.p.125,17:7